

Third Tone Suppression of Distortion Product Otoacoustic Emissions and Their Intracochlear Counterparts in Gerbil

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Abstract. Low-frequency distortion product otoacoustic emissions (DPOAEs) exhibit characteristics that are distinct from their high-frequency counterparts. In this study we investigate the cochlear origin of low-frequency DPOAEs in gerbils by altering local cochlear mechanics via introducing a third interference tone (IT) that varied in frequency and level relative to the DP-evoking stimulus tones. Our findings confirm that an IT suppressed primarily the local-generation component of DPs, which could be predicted by the suppression to the primaries.

INTRODUCTION

Active processes in the cochlea create sounds that leak back out into the ear canal, where they can be recorded as otoacoustic emissions (OAEs)¹. These are complex acoustic signals that are the sum of multiple components that arise from different cochlear regions and varied cochlear mechanisms²⁻⁴. The generation of distortion product otoacoustic emissions (DPOAEs) has been understood to consist of two components that arise from different mechanisms³. First, distortion components originate from the nonlinear interaction of the two primary tones at f_1 and f_2 ($f_2 > f_1$) close to the peak of the f_2 -traveling wave. Second, a reflection component arises when these initial distortion components reflect from cochlear irregularities near the DP frequency (f_{dp}) place.

Recent intracochlear observations using optical coherence tomography (OCT) have revealed that the outer hair cell (OHC) region exhibits broader nonlinear responses at more than one octave below the best frequency (BF), and several published reports⁵⁻⁸ suggest that DPOAEs also include components that arise from cochlear regions that are considerably basal to the f_2 primary-tone place, especially when using high-primary tone levels⁹. Olson and colleagues^{10, 11} have begun to identify the specific conditions that lead to OHC-based cochlear amplification: the amplifying nonlinearity functions as an amplifier at frequencies around the BF where OHC forces input power to the traveling wave¹². The nonamplifying nonlinearity is broadband that represents OHC electromotility and saturates due to OHC current. However, because these forces are not in-phase with basilar membrane (BM) velocity, they cannot supply power into the traveling wave. Dewey¹³ performed a number of suppression experiments and also concluded that the nonamplifying nonlinearity was a local nonlinearity that was not involved in the amplification process at BF. Recently, Ren and He¹⁴ measured two-tone distortion products (DPs), from the reticular lamina (RL) and BM. RL-DPs were significantly larger and occurred over a broader frequency range than BM-DPs. These researchers concluded that primary tones could generate DPs not only at the BF but over a broad region basal to the BF location. It appears that this broadband, nonamplifying nonlinearity could be responsible for generating basal intracochlear DPs that (somehow) emerge from the cochlea to contribute to DPOAEs.

Together, these findings provide all the necessary ingredients to give rise to a basal source of DPs but also raise the question whether these DPs exit the cochlea to contribute to DPOAEs measured in the ear canal. In addition, low-frequency DPOAEs differ from high-frequency ones in that their amplitudes depend less on stimulus frequency separation (i.e. f_2/f_1 ratio), their phase-vs-frequency curves are much steeper, and they are less sensitive to the cochlear

condition^{15,16}. The difference may arise from the signal processing at the apical region compared to the base. That is, apical responses in the OHC region and at the BM are more broadly tuned, and the region of nonlinear BM responses is widened towards lower frequencies¹⁷. To address the generation of low-frequency DPOAEs, we examined the suppression effects of an interference tone (IT) on simultaneously measured DPOAEs and their intracochlear counterparts (DPs) using OCT.

METHODS

Animals: Animal procedures were approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committees (IACUCs) of VA Loma Linda Healthcare System and published¹⁷. Experiments were performed in deeply anesthetized young adult female and male gerbils (*M. unguiculatus*). Each gerbil was anesthetized with a ketamine/xylazine (80 and 10 mg/kg, respectively) cocktail with supplemental doses of anesthesia administered throughout the experiment to maintain areflexia. The left pinna and the cartilaginous ear canal were resected, and the bulla was widely opened to visualize the cochlea. During the experiment, the core temperature was kept at $\sim 38^\circ$ using a heating pad (Harvard Apparatus). At the end of the *in vivo* recordings, the animal was euthanized by anesthetic overdose.

Optical coherence tomography (OCT): Characteristics of our spectral-domain OCT (SDOCT, Thorlabs Telesto III TEL321C1) are detailed and published^{17,18}. Briefly, our OCT system operated with a central wavelength of 1300 nm (bandwidth, 170 nm) and had axial and lateral resolution of $\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$ and $\sim 6 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. OCT system allows us to image the 2nd cochlear turn under a natural status without opening of the cochlea^(17,18, Fig. 2A) and identify key structures of the OCC. Two-dimensional (2D) vibrometry maps were obtained by scanning the OCT's measuring beam across the OCC cross-section: The magnitude and phase reveal the (relative) motions within the OCC cross-section at a particular frequency in detail (Figs. 2B & C). Along a similar vein as the 2D vibrometry maps, we used the OCT data to construct suppression maps for responses at the stimulus and DP frequencies. Comparison of suppression maps from different structures are expected to further explain the cochlear origins of DPOAEs, but also to refine our understanding of the mechanisms that limit the spatial extent over which OHC forces are able to influence the vibrations in the surrounding tissues.

Acoustic Stimulation and Signal Analysis: The tip of a probe that contained a microphone and transducer assembly (ER-10X, Etymotic Research) was placed within a few mm of the tympanic membrane in a closed-field sound configuration, where sound pressure levels were calibrated and are expressed in decibels re. 20 μPa (i.e., dB SPL). Gerbils were stimulated with "zweis" tone complexes, or with equal-level ($L_1=L_2$) two-tone stimuli that had a fixed-frequency ratio of $f_2/f_1=1.25$. For suppression, a third, interference tone (IT; f_3, L_3) was added to the two-tone stimulus. DPOAEs and the intracochlear DPs, specifically the low-frequency sideband DP at $2f_1-f_2$, were extracted from simultaneous measurements in the ear canal using the microphone and 2D vibrometry maps of OCC using OCT. The IT acted as a local or remote suppressor by keeping its frequency (f_3) relatively close to or far from the DP-evoking stimulus frequencies (f_1 and f_2 , respectively) to systematically probe the cochlear region from which DPs contribute to DPOAEs¹⁹. Suppression effects were illustrated by comparing sequential OCC responses and DPOAEs without and with the IT present.

RESULTS

We examined suppression of intracochlear responses at the primary tones and DP frequencies, and simultaneously measured DPOAEs in the ear canal. In healthy gerbil cochleae, when stimulated with two or more tones, robust DPs and DPOAEs were observed. Here we focus on the low-frequency sideband at $2f_1-f_2$. Findings were consistent across animals, with the results presented here being chosen from a subset of 15 experiments to illustrate the main observations. Because of the sensitivity of the OCT system, to obtain clear DP responses with an IT, we needed to use relatively high-level primary tones, i.e., 55- or 65-dB SPL, which broadens the generation of DPs.

1. Low-frequency DPOAEs are from a broader generation region.

We observed that while $2f_1-f_2$ DPOAE were generally robust in gerbils, their sensitivity to suppressors varied with IT frequency (f_3) and level (L_3). Figure 1 shows DPOAE suppression by an IT with an intensity 6 dB greater than the primaries. The suppression effect of the IT can be broadly categorized into two groups based on primary tone

frequency f_2 . For DPOAEs evoked with $f_2 > 4$ kHz suppression was minimal, except when the IT was close to f_2 ($f_3 = f_2 * 1.15$; blue line). This observation aligns with previous studies³ and indicates that high-frequency DPOAEs primarily originate from a limited cochlear region, near the peak of the f_2 traveling wave.

In contrast, DPOAEs evoked with $f_2 < 4$ kHz exhibited suppression even when the IT was more than an octave away from the f_2 frequency (Fig. 1A) and with corresponding phase changes (not shown). Furthermore, suppression was significantly greater compared to that of high-frequency DPOAEs and became more pronounced at lower f_2 frequencies. For example, suppression of up to 25 dB was observed when the IT was close to the primaries ($f_3 = f_2 * 1.15$; blue line in Fig. 1). An intriguing observation was the presence of a maximum suppression for f_2 frequencies between 1.5 to 3 kHz, which corresponding to specific f_3 frequency around 4-5 kHz. The reason for this suppression peak may relate to the middle ear resonance or to the transition between low- and high-frequency cochlear signal processing. The suppressibility of low-frequency DPOAEs over a wider range of IT frequencies implies that they may originate from a broader cochlear region. This suggests that the mechanisms underlying the generation of low-frequency DPOAEs may involve a wider range/extent of cochlear structures or processes.

2. IT suppression of intracochlear responses

FIGURE 2. IT Level- and frequency dependence effects on DPs. (A) OCT image of the OCC cross-section. $2f_1-f_2$ DP 2D maps with variation of IT level (B) and frequency (C). (Expt. LL-07252023, $L_1=L_2=65$ dB SPL, $f_2/f_1=1.25$, $f_2=BF=2.4$ kHz)

To further explore the generation mechanisms of low-frequency DPOAEs, we characterize the intracochlear responses at primary and DP frequencies from an OCC cross-section with a BF between 2 and 2.8 kHz. Figure 2 shows several of OCC 2D vibrometry maps for $2f_1-f_2$ when f_2 was set to $BF=2.4$ kHz, without and with the presence of an IT. Generally, higher IT levels led to increased suppression across the entire OCC (Fig. 2B). With $L_3=L_2+10$ dB, DPs were typically suppressed into the noise. Additionally, the suppression effect of the IT on DPs varied with its frequency. When the IT was closer to the frequency of primary tone f_2 , it suppressed more of the DPs. This is demonstrated in Fig. 2C, where less suppression of OCC motion at the DP frequency occurred when the IT was moved further away from f_2 .

To summarize, we show suppression effects to DPs evoked by sweeping f_1 and f_2 frequencies with a fixed ratio $f_2/f_1=1.25$. Figure 3 illustrates typical responses observed at both the OHC (red) and BM (blue) regions. In general, OHC-DP were larger than BM-DP (solid lines in Figs. 3A-D) especially in the sub-BF region. This observation aligns with previous findings indicating that the OHC region exhibits greater motion than the BM for sub-BF frequencies^{13, 20-22}. Different from the primary tones (not shown), both OHC-DP and BM-DP exhibited multiple peaks including one at $f_2=2.4$ kHz, and another at $f_2=4$ kHz, corresponding to f_2 or $2f_1-f_2$ at the BF^{23, 24}.

To understand the nature of DPs, Figs. 3A'-D' present their phase responses normalized to the primaries. A phase close to $\pm 180^\circ$ or ± 0.5 cycles suggests dominance by a locally-generated component, while departures from

this indicate dominance by non-local components that traveled to the recording location after their generation^{9, 25}. With f_2 below ~ 2 kHz, the phase of unsuppressed DPs was approximately -0.5 cycles, suggesting dominance by a local-generation component. However, at higher f_2 (i.e., $f_2 > 3.4$ kHz), DP phase deviated from -0.5 cycles, indicating that the recorded response was dominated by non-local, traveling components. There was little difference between OHC-DP and BM-DP in this respect.

FIGURE 3. IT frequency dependent suppression on DPs. Amplitude (A-D) and phase (A'-D') for $2f_1-f_2$ DP in the OHC region (red) and on the BM (blue), without (solid line) and with (dashed line) an IT present at various f_3/f_2 ratios. Phase responses were normalized to the primary phases. (Expt. LL-12062023, $L_1=L_2=65$, $f_2/f_1=1.25$, $L_3=L_2+6$)

The dotted lines represent the suppressed DPs with an IT tone. When f_3 was close to f_2 , i.e., $f_3=f_2*1.15$ (Fig. 3A), DPs were suppressed by more than ~ 10 dB at all f_2 frequencies. This, combined with the broadly reduced DPOAEs shown in Fig. 1, suggests that DPs and DPOAEs were primarily generated from a region close to the f_2 peak. As the f_3 frequency moved further away from f_2 , DP suppression was restricted to lower f_2 regions (Figs 3B-D), showing that low-frequency DPs could be suppressed with an f_3 even at a frequency more than one octave above f_2 . The IT also affected the normalized phase of the DP responses (Fig. 3A'-D'), primarily for smaller f_2 , causing a departure from 0.5 cycle. This observation suggests that the IT suppressed more of the local-generation component of DPs in the low-frequency tails of the primary responses, making the non-local (i.e., apical) component dominate the recorded response.

Similar results were obtained across animals. Figure 4 provides a summary of the frequency-dependent effects of the IT on OHC-DPs. To differentiate suppression of the primaries (which caused reduced DP generation) and suppression of the DP themselves, we used the amount of observed primary suppression (variation of displacement in nm of ΔL_1 and ΔL_2 and corresponding phases, respectively) to calculate the vector reduction in DP generation as $\Delta L_1^2 * \Delta L_2$. In general, with $f_2 > 1.5$ kHz, the suppression of OHC-DPs was as expected from the suppression of primaries. This suggests that DP amplitude reductions were not from DP suppression itself, but by the IT effect on the primary tones. For $f_2 < 1.5$ kHz, the DP suppression was less than expected from the reduction in primary levels, probably because our recording location was now far from the BF location, and the recorded DPs were primarily non-locally generated.

FIGURE 4. Mean $2f_1-f_2$ suppression in the OHC region (red line; $L_3=L_2+6$ dB), averaged across animals. Shaded area gives ± 1 std. The IT also (slightly) suppressed the primary tone responses (ΔL_1 and ΔL_2 , respectively), potentially affecting the amplitudes of the generated DP. We calculated $\Delta L_1^2 * \Delta L_2$ to estimate this effect of changed primary levels on the level of the recorded DPs (blue). (A) $f_3=f_2*1.15$; (B) $f_3=f_2*1.4$; (C) $f_3=f_2*1.9$; (D) $f_3=f_2*3$.

DISCUSSION

OHCs have been demonstrated to be a key element in attaining the exquisite sensitivity of the auditory system, compression of response amplitudes, suppression, and generation of DPs²⁶. In the current study, we used OCT to obtain sequentially two- and three-tone induced vibrometry maps of an OCC cross-section at the 2nd turn of gerbil cochlea to establish the correlation between DPs, DPOAEs, and underlying cochlear mechanisms.

Using two-tone stimulation, we observe a complex OCC motion at the DP frequency (Fig. 2), where different structures exhibit varying amplitudes and phases. This intricate motion mirrors the vibration pattern seen at the stimulus frequency (not shown). Furthermore, the OHC-DPs in the sub-BF region are more pronounced than those of the BM (Fig. 3). This observation is consistent with findings at the stimulus frequency, where OHC movements surpass those of the BM, particularly in the sub-BF region¹⁷. Collectively, these results suggest that the newly generated DPs undergo similar signal processing to any stimulus tones. Additionally, the DP components can be classified into distinct groups based on their phase characteristics—local or non-local (likely traveling, Fig. 3)—which is consistent with observations in the basal high-frequency region (e.g.,^{9,25}). This implies that there may not be a straightforward correlation between locally measured DP and their summed responses measured as a DPOAE.

To establish the correlation between DPOAEs and cochlear mechanics, we used an IT to manipulate the cochlear nonlinearity. This is based on the well-known phenomenon of two-tone suppression, which is documented in cochlear microphonics^{27,28}, the auditory nerve^{29,30}, and the mechanical responses of the BM and OHC region^{13,31,32}. It arises when an IT partially saturates the OHC mechano-transduction current. This reduces the magnitudes of that current (and thus OHC-based forces) for the other component(-s) of the stimulus³²⁻³⁴, and linearizes the response. In the presence of an IT, we observe level- and frequency-dependent suppression in responses at both the primary and DP frequencies (Figs. 2 and 4). Generally, an IT tone caused more suppression in the OHC-DP than in the BM-DP, particularly in the sub-BF region and suppressed the local generation component. The reduction in the OHC-DP with an IT tone was consistent with the variation of the primaries at $f_2 > 1.5$ kHz (Fig. 4), confirming that the suppression mechanism reduces the effective level of the primary tones that generate DPs.

Evoked by high-level primary tones at 55- or 65-dB SPL with f_2/f_1 ratio of 1.25, we found that an IT close to f_2 had significant effects on both DPs (Figs. 2-4) and DPOAEs (Fig. 1) at all test frequencies. This observation was consistent with the distortion components originating from a region close to the peak of the f_2 -traveling wave and involving nonlinear distortion processes³. Moving the IT further away from f_2 resulted in minimal suppression of DPs or DPOAEs evoked by $f_2 > 4$ kHz, suggesting that these DPOAEs primarily arise from a location close to the f_2 peak.

On the other hand, low-frequency DPOAEs differ from high-frequency ones^{15,16}, and their generation is less understood. In the current study, we found that the suppression of low-frequency DPOAEs and their intracochlear counterparts, DPs, exhibited at all tested f_3 s; an IT more than one octave above f_2 caused substantial suppression (Figs. 3 & 4). This observation aligns with the broadband nonlinearity in this frequency region^{17,35}. However, when comparing the degree of suppression between the OHC-DPs and DPOAEs, there was no clear relationship between them, except when f_3 was more than one octave above f_2 . This suggests that low-frequency DPOAEs likely originate from a broader region (ongoing research in the lab).

To summarize, our findings suggest low-frequency DPOAEs were from a broad region, i.e., more than one octave basal from the BF. An IT close to the f_2 suppressed the primaries and possible the DPs. Moving the f_3 further away, the suppressions to DPs and DPOAEs were primarily from the suppression of the primaries that interacted over the nonlinear region.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Renata, Sisto]: I read [your paper] with great interest and it will be a pleasure to come back to it with maybe some comments/suggestions/interpretations. I noticed a methodological inaccuracy that I would like to [point out]. You said that you calculated the reduction in DP generation as $DL_1^2 * DL_2$, but you should have calculated the variation of the logarithm of A (or the relative variation of A) where A is $A = csi_1^2 * csi_2$, with csi_1 and csi_2 being the displacements at frequency f_1 and f_2 respectively. DA (dB) = $2DL_1 + DL_2$ where L_1 and L_2 are expressed in dB. You should use this quantity in order to evaluate the relative variation of the DP.

[Wei, Dong]: Thank you for your clarification. The process you described aligns precisely with what we did. Due to page limitations, the methods section did not include this level of detail. We used the measured amplitudes at f_1 and f_2 (in nm) and their phases to calculate the variations with and without an IT. These were then plotted on a dB scale.

[Renata, Sisto]: The question regarding why the DP phase remains at 0 relative to the primaries when you introduce the suppressor. You expected a -180 phase shift due to the back reflection of the DP toward the base. I believe this can be explained by the fact that you are suppressing part of the generation region, and as a result, you are still observing a forward-propagating wave rather than a back-propagating one.

[Wei, Dong]: Thank you. A DP phase of either 0 or 180 degrees relative to the primaries suggests dominance by the local generation component.

[James, Dewey]: Interesting data! I have two main questions: When f_2 and f_1 are varied, is it possible that some of the similarities in suppression of ear canal DPOAEs and intracochlear DPs measured from a single location are somewhat superficial and/or coincidental? In other words, as f_2 is increased above the BF of the intracochlear measurement site, the dominant generation site of the DPOAEs will of course move basal to this site. Suppression of DPOAEs elicited by $f_2 > 4$ kHz therefore presumably has more to do with the properties of locations tuned to > 4 kHz, and less to do with what is happening at the 2-3 kHz place. Can you provide some rationale for comparing the suppression of DPs measured from a single location and suppression of DPOAEs in the ear canal measured over a wide range of f_2 frequencies?

[Wei, Dong]: Thank you for bringing up this question. This is an ongoing project, and we did examine the suppression on DPs and DPOAEs measured simultaneously. As observed in the basal high-frequency region, there was no straightforward correlation between DPs and DPOAEs unless the IT was more than an octave away from f_2 , where the suppression of the locally measured DPs and low-frequency DPOAEs was almost identical. This confirms that the IT tone suppressed the DPs contributing directly to the DPOAEs and the generation region of the DPOAEs.

[James, Dewey]: Does a deviation of the normalized DP phase from 180 degrees necessarily imply the presence of a propagating DP component? In Dong and Olson (2005), the local DP phase (i.e., the DP phase at the output of the nonlinearity) is shown to be either 0 or 180 degrees. This behaviour seems close to what you observe for the normalized DP phase at low f_2 frequencies.

[Wei, Dong]: Our analysis, which includes an examination of the normalized DP phase group delay, associated f_2 frequencies, and model predictions, consistently indicates a dominant non-local component. For further details, refer to the reference provided below.

Bowling et al. (2021) Intracochlear distortion products are broadly generated by outer hair cells but their contributions to otoacoustic emissions are spatially restricted, *Sci Rep.* Jul 1;11(1):13651. doi: 10.1038/s41598-021-93099-7.

[James, Dewey]: I have attached a PDF with more specific comments and suggestions. Enjoy!

[Wei, Dong]: Thank you for your valuable comments. We have revised the manuscript accordingly, with specific modifications to the discussion section, which has been rewritten.

----- during the presentation

[Ernest, Dalhoff]: Very nice experimental data. Maybe you could get the slide where you had the suppression curves of DPOAEs, for the different frequency ratios. Since for each suppression curve you kept your frequency ratio constant, if you were to just, sort of say, now select the most upward point of each curve that you have, you wouldn't come to a curve which goes down at 0 more or less to 1.5 kHz and then falls down to -10 dB, right? And then I would believe that this would probably mimic, I don't have the data in my head for guinea pig, the optimum frequency ratios for the given frequency, then it would probably say that 1.5 to 2kHz is middle ear resonance and below the amplification goes down as it is not so sensitive, the suppression is different. What do you think about that?

[Wei, Dong]: If you're referring to the maximum suppression related to different f_3 frequencies relative to f_2 , this might indicate a middle ear issue. However, the DPOAE phase with an IT (which we did not show here) exhibited

varying degrees of change with different f_3 s. Therefore, the maximum suppression seems to be linked to a transition in cochlear signal processing, specifically from the high-frequency regions of the cochlea to the low-frequency regions.

[Jont, Allen]: Well, kind of an amazing thing was that I was working in the same laboratory long before you got there, and they measured neural tuning curves, and I did the same kinds of experiments but not on the basilar membrane. I did it neurally. The results, in my opinion, are amazing. I'm trying to figure out if it's the same that you're getting. I haven't quite figured that out yet.

[Wei, Dong]: Thank you. I look forward to hearing your explanation.